

Advocacy Proposal

Supporting children with English
as additional language

Presented by: Neharika Verma

April, 2022

Introduction: What we'll discuss

Over a long period of time, New Zealand's Early Childhood Education facilities and surroundings have become more multicultural and multilingual, with tamariki, whanau, and communities from all over the world. (Song, 2020).

Early childhood instructors and groups are working hard to help tamariki whose first language is not English, thanks to multicultural and multi-linguistic whanau in the centres. It's not just important to learn English; it's also important to promote a child's mana, whanau, and community, to provide them a sense of belonging and respect for their own language and cultural knowledge, as well as values in the classroom (Ministry Of Education, 2017).

As a result, it is critical for educators to study, comprehend, and implement programmes and practises that support and uplift multilingual students, particularly in terms of confidence, vocabulary, and English language practise.

This brief study will focus on some of the techniques that help tamariki with English as a second language and their kaiako succeed.

Purpose: why is it required ?

The goal is to assist children and families who may require additional assistance, such as language upskilling or families that are experiencing language barriers in their children's education and learning. As someone who grew up in a family where no one spoke English and faced numerous social, mental, economic, and political barriers as a result of my lack of understanding of the language, it is an extremely relevant and relatable issue to me as an educator because I have the power to help those who face similar challenges. As a result, the focus of this study will be on offering assistance, value, and initiatives to non-English speaking groups. It is critical to concentrate on this cause in order to eliminate linguistic barriers and boost the prospects of development, advancement, and success.

"For many, education is viewed as their family's path to success. Like parents everywhere, they want their children to do well, yet many feel uncertain about a language and culture that is different than their own".

Lee, 1997, p.57

"Power and understanding go hand-in-hand with the capability to communicate. When language boundaries exist, it is frequent to experience frustration, powerlessness, or alienated. Some parents equate a lack of awareness of their language with a lack of admiration for their culture. Although unintended by means of providers, parents may sense rejection and may also isolate themselves further. Parents who don't speak English frequently feel awful about not being able to understand. Out of respect for the teacher, they might also nod affirmatively to remarks without truly appreciating what is being said. Others might also express regret that their English is "not good" and decline to take part in faculty features or take leadership roles"

(Lee, 1997).

Stakeholders

- The child
- Whanau
- the centre and its staff, owner, management
- kaiako
- Ministry
- Community and culture
- Maori

EDUCATION REVIEW OFFICE
Te Tari Arotake Mātauranga

Theoretical perspective: Critical theory

There are a few things to note when we think about planning for tamariki with English as second language.

- 1. It is important that planning strategies incorporate child's first language in daily routine to build that sense of belonging, and comfort for the child. Tamariki and their whanau should feel respected and valued in the center. This allows them to settle easily as well as learn a second language easily. Krashen (1992) found that children who are more proficient in their home language literacy find it easier to develop literacy in their second language. This practice is ensuring that children with bilingual whanau still have access to their language once they leave their houses and that they "experience an environment that values their own and other's languages and cultures" (Ministry Of Education, 1996, p.78). This also supports a child's mana, emotional wellbeing, spiritual wellbeing and whanau wellbeing.**
- 2. Kaiako should encourage whanau participation in the planning process, routinely strategies and plan activities that allow communities and families to be part of child's environment. "Vygotsky's socio-cultural ideas state that learning leads the development and occurs in relationships with people, places and things, mediated by participation in valued social and cultural activities" (Ministry Of Education, 2017,p.61). The best sources of linguistic and cultural knowledge for tamariki comes from the child's family and community itself. . "Funds of knowledge is an approach to curriculum based on the simple premise that "People are competent, they have knowledge, and their life experiences have given them that knowledge" (Gonzalez, Moll & Amanti 2005, pp. ix-x).**
- 3. Modelling the second language using description, music and stories, pictures and peer to peer communication. Allowing tamariki to be each other's tuakana and teina and encouraging peer to peer communication is a proven way of developing linguistic vocabulary and literacy amongst children. The words slowly make sense to children with a demonstration by other children (Ministry Of Education, 2017). It is advocated by Drury, 2013 children's learning, as learning language, social and cultural interaction is connected to socialization (Socio-cultural theory). These conversations can be intigated through activites, play, music, stories, pictures and modelling actions with words for tamariki.**

Benefits of Proposal

Tamariki and whanau	Teachers	the centre
Increased parent participation that will contribute towards the child's learning and development. (Billman 2005, etc.)	encourages effective and reciprocal whanaungatanga with whanau and communities.	ability to provide quality education and supporting different communities and cultures, be known as an environment that is committed towards child's growth, and whanau upliftment .
Motivation to communicate, support, plan for their tamariki, increased confidence and feeling empowered as whanau. "Confidence that their first language is valued and increasing ability in the use of at least one language" (MOE, 2017, P.25)	encourages development of professional practices through research, workshops, approaching support services, and learning about new languages, communities, cultures (Education Review Office, 2022).	allowing new opportunities and situations to unfold that bring different levels of growth and understanding. This ensures that the staff and the environment work together and progress together (Education Review Office, 2022)
increased sense of belonging, feeling of being understood, involved and valued as a learner in the center. empowering mana.	encourages team members to develop plans and strategies, working together as a team with both kaiako and whanau (Education Council, 2017)	ability to plan parent-teacher meetings and workshops to educate whanau and communities about communication as non-english speakers
gives whanau confidence for child and family success. this also results in family wellbeing, mental and spiritual wellbeing of the child, resulting in Holistic development (Ministry Of Education, 2017).	Recognizing and understanding the rights of immigrants, Maori, Pasifika and non english speaking whanau. Looking through unbiased lenses and different perspectives, allowing conversations, devising unique strategies	functioning upto and beyond Ministry standards and receiving high value ERO report which results in success of a center as an education provider (Education Review Office, 2022).

Overview of Plan and actions

acknowledge

Supporting child's first language by acknowledging and incorporating them.

supporting

building confidence in English as second language by modelling language.

involving

involving whanau, first language speakers and English language speakers to support learning

Short term goals

Goal	Action	Support/resource	Graduating teaching standards
Individual Action plans for different children	having individual meetings, planning and strategies for different tamariki based on their needs and English proficiency,	At least a weekly checkup on the plan, regular communication with whanau about interest, progress and communication at home	Standard two C: graduating teachers know how to develop metacognitive strategies for diverse learners
Monthly staff meeting about supporting tamariki with English as a second language.	Discuss with team members individual children's plans including student teachers and relievers to ensure that tamariki have constant support as they require it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pay for monthly meetings, meetings to be timed to encourage staff members, - At least 1 hour staff meeting every week after work to discuss plans 	<p>Standard four A; Graduating teachers draw upon content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge when planning, teaching and evaluating.</p> <p>Standard six B: have the knowledge and dispositions to work effectively with colleagues, parents, whanau and communities</p>
Learning about child's comfort zone - first language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gathering required knowledge and information on the child's first language, culture, and common words from whanau, resources, - incorporating these terms in practice to provide a sense of belonging to child. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - non-contact time for kaiako to research through books, sites, and papers. - written and oral notes from whanau - being able to invite diverse language speakers - teachers, parents or community members 	<p>Standard three A: have an understanding of the complex influences that personal, social, and cultural factors may have on learners</p> <p>Standard Seven C: work cooperatively with those who share responsibility for the learning and well-being of learners.</p>

long term goals

Goal	Action	Support resource	Graduating teaching standards
<p>Increasing tamariki's understanding and vocabulary in English</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - modeling language, actions, and activities in English to tamariki - dual language use for the same actions - the increased use of music, songs, waiatas, picturization to support English vocabulary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>He Kororero: Intentional teaching placards for talking (Ministry of Education, 2017).</i> - working with patience, repeating words and phrases for child to grasp. - Allowing children to communicate with each other: peer to peer communication - asking questions, answering questions, describing their daily routines 	<p>Standard One: Graduating Teachers know what to teach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. have content knowledge appropriate to the learners and learning area of their programme b. have pedagogical content knowledge appropriate to the learners and areas of their programme c. have knowledge of the relevant curriculum documents of Aotearoa New Zealand d. have content and pedagogical content knowledge for supporting English Additional Language (EAL) learners to succeed in the curriculum <hr/> <p>Standard Two: Graduating Teachers know about learners and how they learn</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. have knowledge of a range of relevant theories and research about human development and learning b. have knowledge of a range of relevant theories, principles and purposes of assessment and evaluation c. know how to develop metacognitive strategies of diverse learners d. know how to select curriculum content appropriate to the learners and learning context
<p>Teacher's professional development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - attending seminars, organized workshops about developing language in early years and supporting multi-lingual whanau. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - paid time off for professional development - appropriate resources, funding, invitations from organization through centres are required. 	<p>Standard Seven: Graduating Teachers are committed members of the profession</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. uphold the Education Council's Code of Ethics/Ngā Tikanga Matatika b. have knowledge and understanding of the ethical, professional and legal responsibilities of teachers c. work co-operatively with those who share responsibility for the learning and well-being of learners d. are able to articulate and justify an emerging personal, professional philosophy of teaching and learning
<p>Reflecting on the cycle - supporting first language, developing the second language</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - teaching staff to plan activities that invite multi-lingual people, whanau or community members to engage with tamariki - field trips, park trips, trips to local museum to develop language through experiences, - supporting both first and second language and reviewing this plan every month during meetings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - planning events requires, venue, funding and training of staff. - communication booklets, apps, or pamphlets are ideal for cultural events. - monthly meetings to revisit the plans and reflect on the learning. 	<p>Standard Five: Graduating Teachers use evidence to promote learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. systematically and critically engage with evidence to reflect on and refine their practice b. gather, analyse and use assessment information to improve learning and inform planning c. know how to communicate assessment information appropriately to learners, their parents/caregivers and staff <hr/> <p>Standard Six: Graduating Teachers develop positive relationships with learners and the members of learning communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. recognise how differing values and beliefs may impact on learners and their learning b. have the knowledge and dispositions to work effectively with colleagues, parents/caregivers, families/whānau and communities c. build effective relationships with their learners d. promote a learning culture that engages diverse learners effectively e. demonstrate respect for te reo Māori me ngā tikanga-ā-iwi in their practice

PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE

Standard One:

Graduating Teachers know what to teach

- have content knowledge appropriate to the learners and learning areas of their programme
- have pedagogical content knowledge appropriate to the learners and learning areas of their programme
- have knowledge of the relevant curriculum documents of Aotearoa New Zealand
- have content and pedagogical content knowledge for supporting English as an Additional Language (EAL) learners to succeed in the curriculum

Standard Two:

Graduating Teachers know about learners and how they learn

- have knowledge of a range of relevant theories and research about pedagogy, human development and learning
- have knowledge of a range of relevant theories, principles and purposes of assessment and evaluation
- know how to develop metacognitive strategies of diverse learners
- know how to select curriculum content appropriate to the learners and the learning context

Standard Three:

Graduating Teachers understand how contextual factors influence teaching and learning

- have an understanding of the complex influences that personal, social and cultural factors may have on teachers and learners
- have knowledge of tikanga and te reo Māori to work effectively within the bicultural contexts of Aotearoa New Zealand
- have an understanding of education within the bicultural, multicultural, social, political, economic and historical contexts of Aotearoa New Zealand

PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE

Standard Four:

Graduating Teachers use professional knowledge to plan for a safe, high quality teaching and learning environment

- draw upon content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge when planning, teaching and evaluating
- use and sequence a range of learning experiences to influence and promote learner achievement
- demonstrate high expectations of all learners, focus on learning and recognise and value diversity
- demonstrate proficiency in oral and written language (Māori and/or English), in numeracy and in ICT relevant to their professional role
- use te reo Māori me ngā tikanga-ā-iwi appropriately in their practice
- demonstrate commitment to and strategies for promoting and nurturing the physical and emotional safety of learners

Graduating Teachers Standards (New Zealand Teachers Council, 2007)

Standard Five:

Graduating Teachers use evidence to promote learning

- systematically and critically engage with evidence to reflect on and refine their practice
- gather, analyse and use assessment information to improve learning and inform planning
- know how to communicate assessment information appropriately to learners, their parents/caregivers and staff

PROFESSIONAL VALUES AND RELATIONSHIPS

Standard Six:

Graduating Teachers develop positive relationships with learners and the members of learning communities

- recognise how differing values and beliefs may impact on learners and their learning
- have the knowledge and dispositions to work effectively with colleagues, parents/caregivers, families/whānau and communities
- build effective relationships with their learners
- promote a learning culture that engages diverse learners effectively
- demonstrate respect for te reo Māori me ngā tikanga-ā-iwi in their practice

Standard Seven:

Graduating Teachers are committed members of the profession

- uphold the Education Council's Code of Ethics/Ngā Tikanga Matatika
- have knowledge and understanding of the ethical, professional and legal responsibilities of teachers
- work co-operatively with those who share responsibility for the learning and well-being of learners
- are able to articulate and justify an emerging personal, professional philosophy of teaching and learning

These standards recognise that the Treaty of Waitangi extends equal status and rights to Māori and Pākehā alike.

Graduates entering the profession will understand the critical role teachers play in enabling the educational achievement of all learners.

GRADUATING TEACHER
STANDARDS:
AOTEAROA NEW ZEALAND

EDUCATION COUNCIL
NEW ZEALAND | Matatū Aotearoa

Unique place of Maori

“Te Reo Māori is a taonga under article two of Te Tiriti o Waitangi. Fostering the learning and use of te reo Māori is the responsibility of all kaiako and the education system as a whole” (Ministry of Education, 2017).

Inclusive practice involves acknowledging, respecting and incorporating languages of tamariki especially Maori which is a national treasure. Our commitment to Treaty Of Waitangi guides our practice as kaiako to value and use Te Reo Maori in our daily practice and encourage tamariki to speak Te Reo Maori as well. Kaiako shall model the language by speaking it daily in short phrases, keywords, waiatas, songs, stories and care routines. Maori vocabulary can be developed by using Maori terms for instructions, questions, objects, colours, numbers, food items, and describing simple actions to tamariki. Te Reo Maori has a unique place in Aotearoa and should be fostered more in learning by educators (Ministry Of Education, 2017). Maori knowledge and learning can be best extended by Maori whanau and local communities around the center. Te Whaariki says that “Children’s learning and development is enhanced when culturally appropriate ways of communicating are used and when parents, whānau and community are encouraged to participate in and contribute to the curriculum” (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.20). Events, weekly meetups or getting to know local iw and communities can be quite helpful in developing Te Reo Maori proficiency and understanding past, present and future of the community.

Common Māori Phrases in the Classroom

Commands

Turituri!	Be quiet!
Tītiro (mai)	Look (this way)
Taihoa	Wait
Kaua e pēnā!	Don't do that!
Kia tere!	Be quick / Quickly!
Kāti	That's enough
Whai mai!	Follow me!
Kia tau	Be still, Settle down

Questions

Kei hea tō pene rākau?	Where is your pencil?
Nā wai tēnei pukapuka?	Whose book is this?
Kei hea ia?	Where is he/she?
Kua reri?	Are you ready?
Kei hea tō ...?	Where's your ...?
Kei a wai ...?	Who has got ...?

Possible Challenges

- Not having enough resources or culturally diverse teachers that could understand child's first language
- not having enough funding to invite local iwis, plan events, plan visits or organize meetups, funding is also required for professional development workshops and weekly meetings
- children finding it hard to settle in and feeling "out of place" because of language differences
- New teachers and relievers not being aware of individual child plans that may affect child's progress. E.g using english with a child who is yet to understand the language.

Possible Solutions

- employing and encouraging culturally diverse/multi-lingual kaiako in the center
- New staff and relievers to be given brief insight on children's individual plans after working hours.
- Requesting funding from Ministry, looking at free workshops, fundraising for events like cultural fest or field trip, trip to museum, requesting local iwi for workshops with whanau and kaiako
- making whanau aware of individual child plans and involve them in weekly reports and meetings to encourage continuation of plan at home
- making whanau aware of ministry documents and center policies
- allowing whanau to have some time with child during first few days, making kaiako aware of any verbal phrases child is aware of. Noting down oral and written keywords from child's first language to provide a sense of belonging to the child.

References

- Billman, N., Geddes, C., & Hedges, H. (2005). *Teacher-parent partnerships: Sharing understandings and making changes*. *Australian Journal of Early Childhood*, 30, 44-48.
- Drury R. (2013). How silent is the 'Silent Period' for young bilinguals in early years settings in England?, *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 21:3, 380-391, DOI: 10.1080/1350293X.2013.814362
- Education Council. (2017). *Our code, our standards*. Ngā Tikanga Matatika, Ngā Paerewa. Education Council.
<https://teachingcouncil.nz/assets/Files/Code-and-Standards/Our-Code-Our-Standards-Nga-Tikanga-Matatika-Nga-Paerewa.pdf>.
- Education Review Office. (2022). ***Responding to Diverse Cultures: Good Practice in Home-based Early Childhood Services***.
- Gonzalez, N., Moll, L.C. & Amanti, C. (2005). *Funds of knowledge: Theorizing practices in households, communities, and classrooms*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates
- Krashen, S. (1992). *Fundamentals of language education*. Torrance, CA: Laredo Publishing.
- Ministry of Education (1996) *Te Whāriki: He whāriki mātauranga mō ngā mokopuna o Aotearoa. Early childhood curriculum*. Wellington, New Zealand: Learning Media
- Ministry of Education (2017). NGĀ RAUEMI WHAKAKŌRERO, *Te kōrerorero - Talking together*. New Zealand: Learning Media.
- Ministry of Education (2017). *Te Whāriki. He Whāriki mātauranga mō ngā mokopuna o Aotearoa. Early childhood curriculum*. Wellington, New Zealand: Learning Media.
- Lee, L. (1997). Working with non-English-speaking families. *Child Care Information Exchange*, 57-57.
- Song, H. H. (2020). *The Challenges and Benefits of Maintaining ECE Children's Home Languages in New Zealand* (Doctoral dissertation, Auckland University of Technology).